

NASA's ADVANCED COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY SATELLITE PROGRAM AND ITS APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Advanced Communications Technology Satellite (ACTS) Program is developing a variety of new satellite communication technologies and, through its Experiments Program, promoting the applications that will use this technology. Examples of the developmental technologies include 30/20-GHz components, 110-Mbps time-division multiple access (TDMA), on-board digital signal regeneration and switching, and multibeam antennas. Various Earth station developments such as Jet Propulsion Laboratory's (JPL's) Advanced Mobile Terminal, the Harris T1 Very Small Aperture Terminal (VSAT), the Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) Ultra Small Aperture Terminal, and the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) High Data Rate (HDR) Earth Station are underway that will access the unique capabilities of the ACTS. This paper briefly summarizes the technologies and the applications that will be demonstrated during the ACTS operational phase scheduled to begin in April 1993.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of satellite technology has been aided at least in part through NASA's research and development satellite communications programs. The Relay Project, which launched a satellite into low-Earth orbit in 1962, represented NASA's first major research and development satellite communications project. The Relay Project demonstrated that communications equipment could be flown and that low-orbit satellites would be an operational nightmare for any sizeable number of Earth stations. The NASA Syncom program grew out of these results and explored satellite communications at geosynchronous orbit. Two Syncom satellites successfully attained geosynchronous orbit in 1963 and 1964 and demonstrated the operational feasibility of communications at that orbit. All subsequent geosynchronous satellites (communications, meteorological, etc.) can trace their origin to the Syncom satellites.

NASA followed the Syncom program with the development and flight of a series of Advanced Technology Satellites (ATS). Six ATS launches were made between 1966 and 1974 to conduct experiments and demonstrate major advances in communications and spacecraft technology. L-band work by NASA on ATS-5 led to the Marisat series

of satellites which support communications with ships at sea. The ATS-6 demonstrated the feasibility of deploying large (9-m) antennas in orbit and provided access for experimentation with two-way Very Small Aperture Terminal (VSAT) data communications at Ku-band (14/12 GHz) in advance of licensing of commercial service of that frequency band by the Federal Communications Commission. The joint Canadian/NASA Communications Technology Satellite (CTS) followed the ATS series and provided direct demonstrations of direct to home television and the utility of the 12-GHz band for this service.

NASA's current research and development satellite communications effort is the Advanced Communications Technology Satellite (ACTS) Program. Satellite technology has evolved through the progression of component refinement, higher frequency operation, and the development and refinement of transmission protocols. The ACTS Program also continues along that path with the development of transmit, receive, and antenna technologies in the Ka frequency band (30/20 GHz). ACTS employs dynamic Forward Error Correction, but in addition, the ACTS incorporates technology widely accepted throughout the satellite community as the next logical progression in satellite technology: on-board processing and switching.

II. ACTS SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The ACTS, which is scheduled for launch aboard the shuttle in February 1993, will be maneuvered to a geosynchronous orbit at 100° West. The ACTS system incorporates many newly developed technologies not yet common in the commercial marketplace, such as Ka-band multibeam antennas, on-board digital regeneration, on-board nx64 kbps circuit switching, real-time circuit allocation, and transponders of 900-MHz bandwidth. These key characteristics, among others, form the platform supporting the subsequent development of a variety of Earth station configurations.

The increased antenna gain at the higher Ka-band frequencies and the advanced transmission and reception characteristics of the ACTS satellite enable the Earth station to communicate at high data rates while employing small diameter antenna and low power transmitters. The spot beams formed by the multibeam antennas of the ACTS have 0.5° beamwidth, (about 150 miles diameter at

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the surface of the earth) using antenna sizes of 2.2 and 3.3-m for receive and transmit, respectively. The spot beams typically will have an Effective Isotropic Radiated Power (EIRP) of about 63 dB-W and a gain-to-temperature ratio (G/T's) of about 18 dB/K. In addition to the multi-beam antennas there is a mechanically steerable antenna that can be employed to place a spot beam of 1.0° beamwidth anywhere in the view of the ACTS: roughly, the western hemisphere including Alaska and Hawaii. Fig. 1 shows the coverage area of ACTS.

Fig. 1 ACTS coverage area

On-board digital regeneration represents a distinct advantage over frequency-translation-oriented communication satellites. On the ACTS satellite, on-board demodulators transform incoming TDMA bursts into a digital stream. The digital stream is demultiplexed into 64-kbps channels and fed into one of two baseband processors for subsequent circuit-switched routing. The outputs of the baseband processor are then multiplexed into digital streams and transformed into TDMA bursts for downlink transmission. Through this process the timing and information content of the digital transmission stream is regenerated yielding an approximate 2.8-dB increase of Energy-per-bit to noise-density ratio (E_b/N_0) in comparison to direct frequency translation [1].

The nx64 kbps circuit switching of the on-board baseband processors creates virtual circuit paths between Earth stations residing in separate beams of the ACTS satellite. Two parallel baseband processors, each capable of routing 1728 individual 64-kbps circuits, effect the interconnection between the ACTS beams. Incoming TDMA bursts are demodulated and demultiplexed into individual 64-kbps signals presented to the baseband processors. Real-time circuit switch routing is enabled via a low-data-rate communication path between each Earth station and the Master Control Station (MCS) based at the NASA Lewis Research Center, Cleveland, Ohio. This communication

path is integrated into the ACTS TDMA burst structure and allows the Earth station and Master Control Station (MCS) to exchange circuit setup and disconnect messages as well as other messages.

The MCS creates a routing table based on the circuit commands exchanged with the Earth stations. This routing table is transmitted to the satellite where it is implemented by the baseband processor, establishing nx64-kbps channels between Earth stations. Existing channels between Earth stations remain intact while new circuits are established. The time between a circuit request and its actual creation varies according to the number of outstanding requests and network traffic, but it is estimated to be less than 4.5 sec. under all but the most extreme circumstances.

The preceding passages describe the ACTS Baseband Processor Mode of operation. Another mode of ACTS operation is the Microwave Switch Matrix (MSM) Mode, through which the 900-MHz bandwidth capacity of each of the three Ka-Band ACTS transponders is made available through commands issued by the MCS to the satellite. In this mode of operation, beam locations are interconnected via an analog microwave switch matrix rather than by the digitally oriented baseband processor. The MSM has bandwidth characteristics matching those of the transponders. This bandwidth, coupled with the high EIRP and dB/K of the ACTS satellite, have made it possible to pursue the development of High Data Rate (HDR) Earth Stations described later in this paper.

III. PROPAGATION EXPERIMENTS

A thorough characterization of the propagation environment will permit effective use of the 20/30-GHz frequency bands for satellite communications. The ACTS beacons at 20 and 27.5 GHz will be used to (1) determine the dynamics of fade depths, duration, and rates of change at these frequencies; (2) suggest techniques that compensate for impediments to effective communications at these frequencies; and (3) contribute to the refinement of models for predicting attenuation statistics [2].

Rain attenuation is a major impediment to satellite communications at 20/30 GHz. It presents a unique challenge to satellite system designers because it is more severe than rain attenuation found in other, lower frequency bands currently used for commercial communication satellites. At these higher frequencies, other phenomena become significant and must be accounted for in designing a satellite system. Attenuation losses due to clouds and oxygen can be significant. Another factor to be considered is tropospheric scintillation.

Development of a prototype propagation terminal for ACTS began in 1991 and is now nearing completion. Activity began in February 1992 to build eight production propagation terminals. These terminals, which are scheduled to be completed on October 1, 1992 will be supplied to propagation researchers at participating universities and other institutions. The eight terminals will be identical and

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will be delivered with a common set of preprocessing software, thus assuring a uniformity in data handling and data formats for comparison of statistics across all locations, permitting collection of data in several rain climate zones. Propagation measurements will begin as early as possible because of the long observation times required to obtain accurate statistics. Plans call for all eight propagation terminals to be completed and installed in the field by the date that ACTS is available for experimentation.

IV. APPLICATIONS

The combination of the different technologies incorporated into the ACTS has created a unique platform allowing the development of a variety of applications. The applications of the ACTS are centered around the different terminal types that are being developed to use the ACTS; that is, the T1 VSAT, the HDR Earth Station, and the Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) terminal, and the Land-Mobile Aeronautical equipment. Each of the terminals exploits a different characteristic of the ACTS in support of its operation.

A. T1 Very Small Aperture Terminal (VSAT)

The ACTS T1 VSAT is a small terminal that can be sited on user premises (see Fig. 2) and provides twenty-eight 64-kbps interconnect service over the ACTS in a mesh network configuration. The T1 VSAT can be operated within any of the spot beams depicted in Fig. 1. The antenna sizes available for the T1 VSAT are 1.2 and 2.4-m. The T1 VSAT accesses the baseband processor of the ACTS, and signaling generated by the T1 VSAT controls the ACTS switching characteristics in real time. From the user's point of view, ACTS will be a modern digital telephone central office.

Fig. 2 ACTS T1 VSAT, 1.2-m antenna

The T1 VSAT's under production by Harris Government Systems Division, Melbourne, Florida, extend the switching capability of the ACTS to the local loop or network. The terrestrial interface equipment (TIE) component of the T1

VSAT is a modular digital switch providing the services of a central office (CO) or a Private Branch Exchange (PBX). The TIE is an off-the-shelf unit, supplied by Redcom, Inc., that has been integrated into the T1-VSAT. The TIE provides standard telephony interconnects: T1 digital trunks at 1.544 Mbps, analog trunks and local loop lines. Also provided are the standard user signaling tones such as dial tones, busy tones, and push button tones.

B. Integrated Services Digital Network (ISDN) Option

To fully demonstrate the digital switching nature of the ACTS, an Integrated Services Digital Network (ISDN) option has been developed to supplement the basic operation of the T1 VSAT. ISDN is the name given to the protocols and services that the telephony environment is implementing globally to extend digital capabilities to end users. Basic Rate Interface (BRI) ISDN will provide the end user two 64 Kbps circuits and a 16-kbps signaling channel to the terminating CO or PBX. BRI supports voice and data services. Primary Rate Interface (PRI) ISDN has twenty-three, 64-kbps circuits and a 64-kbps signaling channel. PRI is generally used to connect PBX's to CO's in the ISDN environment.

The level of ISDN service chosen for implementation in the ACTS T1 VSAT is the PRI. The ACTS T1 VSAT PRI will provide ISDN services and be compatible with terrestrial ISDN services. The ACTS ISDN system will support services for circuit switched and packet switched connections such as 64-kbps speech, 64-kbps unrestricted digital services, 3.1 kHz audio, X.25 virtual calls, and X.25 permanent virtual circuits. Additional services provided by the ACTS ISDN interface include bundled channel bandwidths of unrestricted digital transmission rates of 2x64, 384, and 1472 kbps.

C. Land-Mobile and Aeronautical Program Development

Ka-band has outstanding promise for mobile communications because of its available bandwidth and its potential for use with significantly smaller equipment for users. Some of the challenges that exist at the Ka-band include (1) a young technology with lossy RF components, (2) significant rain attenuation, (3) potentially large frequency uncertainty, and (4) large Doppler shifts during mobile operation [3].

In response to these challenges, the Jet Propulsion Laboratory has been developing the Advanced Mobile Terminal (AMT) as a proof-of-concept breadboard devised to overcome the challenges of Ka-band land-mobile communications. The AMT operates in the ACTS MSM Mode of operation. An unmodulated pilot is retransmitted from a fixed station to the AMT at an offset frequency from the user information channel. This pilot is used by the AMT to aid antenna tracking, as a frequency reference for Doppler correction, and in measuring rain attenuation. The Doppler shift of the pilot signal detected by the AMT is used to pre-compensate the return (AMT transmission) link. This significantly improves signal performance at the fixed station and reduces the size of guard bands that would be required otherwise.

The data rate of the AMT is selectable among 2.4, 4.8, and 9.6 kbps; a higher rate of 64 kbps can be supported under restricted link conditions. To increase system availability and service continuity, the AMT will select data rates as a function of the rain attenuation detected in the forward and return links. The speech codec of the AMT converts analog speech signals into representative digital streams at data rates of 2.4, 4.8, and 9.6 kbps, with monotonically improving voice quality. The speech codec also has an interface that supports connection to the Public Switch Telephone Network.

Two types of antenna are under development for the AMT. The first is a "passive" elliptical reflector-type using a high performance amplifier (HPA). The second is an "active" array antenna with Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuit HPA's and Low Noise Amplifiers integrated onto the array. Either of the two antenna types will be mated to a mechanical steering system encased inside a radome with a diameter of 8 in. and maximum height of 3.5 in.

The ACTS Program Office, Jet Propulsion Laboratory, and NASA Lewis Research Center are collaborating in a demonstration of a modified AMT operating in the aeronautical environment. High Doppler offsets and Doppler rates are inherent in this environment because of high aircraft cruise speeds, banking maneuvers, and Ka-band operating frequencies. The experiment will demonstrate continuous maintenance of the duplex information link as the aircraft flies through a series of the ACTS spot beams. The experimentation is expected to begin in January 1994 and to continue through June 1994.

Although ACTS is an experimental satellite, future systems will share several of its characteristics including multiple spot-beam antennas and uplink power control. Operational mobile systems of the future will face many of the challenges addressed by the experimental work done with ACTS.

D. Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA)

SCADA applications can be supported through ACTS technology and will result in reduced antenna size and transmit power requirements. This, in turn, can potentially lead to lower operational system costs [4].

SCADA systems typically involve a central processing point collecting real-time process information from dispersed points for purposes of monitoring and/or process control. Systems of this type are employed in electric, gas, and water utilities, oil and gas production fields, and gas pipeline systems. SCADA applications are one example of a much broader class of potential low-data throughput applications. This general class of applications represents a large market that can be serviced cost effectively as the result of decreasing costs of transmission systems possible through ACTS technology.

The analysis of an ACTS SCADA system has been a classic example of NASA working with end users and service providers to define a new service offering. A functional specification for an operational SCADA system was developed by a working group of potential end users.

A manufacturer's study was then performed by Hughes Network Systems working cooperatively with GE Astro Space Division.

The baseline system developed in the Hughes study consisted of a single satellite, on shared hub station, and 400,000 SCADA units. The design allowed a wide mixture of polling rates but an average polling rate of 32 polls per hour (1 poll/1.9 min.) was assumed. The estimated cost of this system was \$77/Earth station/month. The most critical component of the system cost was the price of the SCADA Earth Station at about \$1500/unit; accounting for more than 80% of the total system cost.

The baseline SCADA Earth Station would have an antenna diameter of less than one foot, a transmitting power of .25 Watt, and would exhibit an availability of 99.9%.

As an output of these studies, NASA will develop a compatible Ka-band transceiver section that would allow any compatible Ku-band design to be tested at the Ka-band with a smaller antenna and lower power final transmitter stage. The converted Earth Station may then be evaluated using the ACTS. This approach is intended to reduce the cost and technical risks of evaluating Ka-band versions of future SCADA Ka-band systems prior to the availability of commercial Ka-band satellite service.

E. High Data Rate (HDR) Earth Station

As another example of the collaborative environment fostered by the ACTS Program, NASA has entered into a joint program with the Defense Advanced Research Project Agency (DARPA) to develop an High Data Rate (HDR) system that will exploit the high-speed capabilities of the ACTS satellite. The HDR system will be used for advanced applications and experiments involving satellite and satellite terrestrial networks.

The HDR Program is being undertaken by DARPA in its role as Gigabit Testbed Project Manager in the federally sponsored National Research and Education Network (NREN) effort. The NREN Program has as one of its goals the development and implementation of a national network capable of supporting transmission rates in excess of 1 Gbps. To date, DARPA has funded five testbeds for the development of gigabit networking technologies. The joint NASA ACTS/DARPA effort will result in the creation of a sixth testbed which will focus on the development of innovative applications using the high-speed satellite environment and hybrid satellite-fiber interconnections.

In this joint undertaking, NASA and DARPA will cooperate to define and fund an ACTS HDR system. DARPA has a particular interest in developing networking technologies and will fund the development of the system's networking characteristics. NASA will assist DARPA in the development of the system and manage its operation, after completion. DARPA, again in its role as the NREN Gigabits Testbed Project Manager, will fund and manage a group of experiments that will use the ACTS HDR system.

On January 6, 1992, DARPA placed a Broad Agency Announcement (BAA) in the Commerce Business Daily requesting proposals for the development of an ACTS

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HDR Earth Station system. Approximately \$7 million of NASA and DARPA funds have been budgeted for the development of the HDR system. The BAA gave general guidelines allowing contractors to propose innovative systems that may not otherwise be considered. These guidelines were that the requested system will have a minimum of five Earth stations, capable of transmitting at least 160 Mbps with a end-to-end bit error rate of less than 10^{-11} . At least three of the Earth stations are to be transportable such that they can be set up and operated within one week of arrival at an installation site. The antenna size for the transportable units is not to exceed 5 meters in diameter. All the Earth stations of this system are to operate unattended and use standard 110 Vac at 60 Hz. Final proposals for this system were due February 24, 1992. Selection for award will occur as soon as possible afterwards.

In 1990, DARPA released BAA #90-13, the first of two Broad Agency Announcements soliciting the development of applications for operation over the ACTS satellite. A proposal submitted by the Ohio Supercomputer Center to this first solicitation entitled "Online Steering of Scientific Simulations Using the NASA ACTS" has been selected by DARPA. Their proposal involves spatially separated collaborators manipulating a supercomputer based visualization model in real time. The ACTS HDR system is to provide the networking necessary for this application. A DARPA sponsored BAA is expected to be released in the near future soliciting additional HDR experimenters.

Other experiments involving the developed system, outside of the current DARPA commitment, are expected and some proposals have been submitted to the ACTS Program through the NASA Experiment Opportunity Announcement (EOA), dated August 16, 1991. Proposals may still be submitted through the EOA regarding this system. NASA's intent is to support industry experimentation with the HDR system to the fullest extent possible.

V. SUMMARY

The ACTS experiments program currently has a funded life of 2 years commencing with the launch of the ACTS in February 1993. If additional funds are acquired, the ACTS can operate for approximately an additional two years before it exhausts station keeping fuel. Throughout the life of ACTS it is expected that many new satellite applications will be demonstrated first on ACTS as has occurred in the past through the Relay, Syncom, ATS, and CTS programs.

VI. REFERENCES

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